

TITANIUM BUTYL-PHOSPHATE GRAFTED MESOPOROUS SILICA HYBRID COMPOSITE FOR RARE EARTH SEPARATION

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ABSTRACT

Rare earth elements (REEs), composed by all lanthanides plus scandium and yttrium, have found use in modern high-tech applications including permanent magnets, fluorescent lamps and catalytic converters. It is worth noting that certain application of REEs requires ultra-purity of one element despite their shared chemical properties. Separation and purification therefore becomes an important task. Commercially, the REEs are now separated by solvent extraction technology and the high-purity REEs are produced by ion-exchange process. In recent years, the recycling of REEs from industrial waste streams has received more and more attention [1].

Tri-*n*-butyl phosphate (TBP) is a typical extractant used in solvent extraction of REEs. Neutral REE-nitrate complexes can be dissolved into TBP-organic phase and the slight differences in the formation constants of different REE-nitrate complexes result in preferential extraction. In this abstract, we present the covalent anchoring of butyl-phosphate group onto titanium modified mesoporous MCM-41 silica. The hybrid composites were synthesized through layer-by-layer chemical grafting techniques based on the report by J. Zhang [2]. Briefly, the MCM-41 silica was first grafted with -Ti-OH through the reaction with titanium isopropoxide and subsequent hydrolysis in water. The surface titanol groups were then reacted sequentially with phosphorus oxychloride and butanol. The overall synthesis procedure is illustrated in Fig. 1. The final product is denoted as MCM-41-TiBuP. For comparison, we prepared also MCM-41-Titanium Phosphate (MCM-41-TiP) in which the last synthetic step utilized water instead of butanol.

Figure 1: Layer-by-layer grafting of MCM-41 silica with titanium butyl-phosphate.

The prepared material was characterized by chemical composition analysis, X-ray powder diffraction (XRD), thermogravimetric analysis coupled with mass spectrometry (TGA-MS) as well as scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Chemical analysis showed the MCM-41-TiBuP contained 8.4% of Ti and 4.0% of P. XRD pattern and SEM images revealed that the grafted material retained original pellet structure with mesoporosity. TGA-MS confirmed the chemical binding of butyl group through the release of butane at ca. 550 °C.

The sorption behavior of the prepared material was assessed in a batch mode with 1 mM equimolar mixture of Sc-Nd-Dy, a solid to liquid ratio of 50 mg/20 mL and the equilibrium pH at around 2.3. The presence of butyl-phosphate group on the surface of the hybrid material granted it with neutral extraction capability. However, it is expected that not all of the silanol and titanol groups

were effectively reacted in the synthesis. The remaining silanol and titanol groups could serve as ion-exchange sites for REEs. To facilitate the formation of neutral complexes and inhibit the ion-exchange sites, ammonium nitrate (0, 1 and 5 M) was added to the solution. The resulting separation factors (SFs) between Sc/Nd and Sc/Dy were listed in Table 1.

Material	Ammonium nitrate (M)	SF (Sc/Nd)	SF (Sc/Dy)
MCM-41-TiP	0	216	111
MCM-41-TiP	1	88	55
MCM-41-TiP	5	139	76
MCM-41-TiBuP	0	372	321
MCM-41-TiBuP	1	166	138
MCM-41-TiBuP	5	2471	542

Table 1: SFs between Sc/Nd and Sc/Dy in the studied system.

With the increase of nitrate concentration from 0 to 1 M, the SFs decreased due to the uptake sacrificed by the competing cation exchange (NH_4^+) process. When the nitrate concentration reached 5 M, more stable REE-nitrate complexes are formed. The stability constants of REE-nitrate complexes are larger when the ionic radius of certain REE is smaller. Therefore, high separation factors between Sc/Nd and Sc/Dy were found at ammonium nitrate concentration of 5 M. More detailed characterizations are in need to fully elucidate the sorption mechanism of the newly prepared hybrid material.

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. Dupont and K. Binnemans, Rare-earth recycling using a functionalized ionic liquid for the selective dissolution and revalorization of $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ from lamp phosphor waste, *Green Chemistry*, **17**, 2015, pp. 856-868 (doi: [10.1039/C4GC02107J](https://doi.org/10.1039/C4GC02107J)).
- [2] J. Zhang, Z. Ma, J. Jiao, H. Yin, W. Yan, E. W. Hagaman, J. Yu and S. Dai, Layer-by-Layer Grafting of Titanium Phosphate onto Mesoporous Silica SBA-15 Surfaces: Synthesis, Characterization, and Applications, *Langmuir*, **25**, 2009, pp. 12541-12549 (doi: [10.1021/la9017486](https://doi.org/10.1021/la9017486)).